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THE ROLE OF Ni ADDITIVE, SIZE FACTOR AND SURFACE CHEMICAL STATE IN DECREASING TEMPERATURE AND IMPROVING DECOMPOSITION KINETICS OF THE NANOSIZED MgH₂ HYDRIDE PHASE OF MECHANICAL ALLOYS Mg +10wt.% Ni AND MgH₂ +10wt.% Ni

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Abstract

Three hydride-forming mechanical alloys of magnesium with the addition of 10 wt % Ni were synthesized. The mechanical alloys were derived by the method of reactive mechanical alloying (RMA) by different ways, in particular by reactive grinding of Mg powder with Ni additive and by the same reactive grinding under the same conditions of two MgH₂ powders made using different methods with the same Ni additives. The effect of this Ni additive and the method of obtaining mechanical alloys (MAs) on the hydrogen sorption properties, temperature and kinetics of decomposition of their MgH₂ hydride phase was investigated by isobaric thermodesorption spectroscopy (TDS) at a constant hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa. The appreciable influence of the applied method of obtaining MAs on the kinetics of the process of hydrogen desorption is established and the mechanism of the specified influence is investigated.

Keywords: mechanical alloy; hydrogen-sorption properties; hydrogenation / dehydrogenation kinetics; thermal stability, hydride phase, thermal desorption spectroscopy

1. Introduction

The widespread introduction of hydrogen technologies and fuel cells requires further fundamental and engineering research towards the creation of new materials for hydrogen storage. In contrast to the use of compressed hydrogen, an efficient and safe storage method is chemical bonding of hydrogen in metal hydrides (MH). The latest research on materials for storing hydrogen is largely devoted to magnesium hydride MgH₂ and its alloys, which are obtained using the methods of mechanochemistry [1-8]. The results obtained indicate that the latter methods have improved hydrogen sorption capacities, kinetic characteristics and cyclic stability, making it realistic to create high-capacitive and highly efficient materials for hydrogen storage and their practical use at ambient conditions [9]. As the analysis of works [10-24] shows, some researchers managed to significantly improve the kinetics of absorption-desorption of hydrogen by magnesium-based alloys. At the same time, the thermodynamic stability and the decomposition temperature of their hydrides still remain high enough for the practical use of these materials as hydrogen accumulators in vehicles; however, there is a prospect of their use in stationary hydrogen storage systems.

Researches carried out by scientists in the last 10-15 years were aimed at creating technologies for the manufacture of high-capacity hydrogen-sorbing materials based on magnesium with a set of characteristics that ensure practical use in stationary hydrogen storage systems. The development of effective technologies for the modification and alloying of magnesium-based materials is based on the results of previous studies: the relationship between the state of

the surface of hydrides [25], the kinetics of their formation/decomposition, the discovered correlation between the hydrogen sorption and thermodynamic properties of hydrides and the contribution of various components (primarily ionic) into the chemical "hydrogen - metal" bond [26-32]. The results of the studies of the role of a small additive (10 wt. %) separately of the alloying elements Ti, Fe, Ni in reducing thermal stability and improving the decomposition kinetics of stoichiometric hydride MgH₂ (obtained by reactive mechanical alloying (RMA) for 10 hours of grinding Mg powder and powder of one of these transition metals) [9] showed a very fast kinetics of hydrogen desorption at pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor and temperature of 300 °C for Mg + 10 Me wt. % mixtures versus pure Mg. In particular, the time for the release of 50 % of the total amount of hydrogen was 7, 13 and 16.5 minutes when adding to Mg 10 wt. % Ni, Fe and Ti, respectively, and with the release of all amount of hydrogen over 14, 50 and 50 min in those cases. The obtained experimental data revealed that among the three transition metals used as an alloying element, the fastest kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH₂ hydride phase of the obtained mechanical alloys (MAs) is provided by Ni not only due to good catalytic properties but also its significant effect on surface chemical state. It was also found that the further improvement of the kinetics of the hydrogen desorption process, namely the increase of almost twice the rate of hydrogen evolution from the MgH₂ hydride phase of the mechanical alloy Mg + 10 wt. % Ni can be carried out by increasing the time of reactive grinding from 10 to 20 hours of a mixture of powders consisting of Mg and Ni. The results of these previous studies of the present authors

were used in defining the purpose of this work. The effect of an additive to magnesium of 10 wt. % Ni on the kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase of mechanical alloys was studied in Refs. [10, 16, 22]. The mechanical alloys were obtained by two different manners: grinding a mixture of commercial MgH_2 and Ni powders [16, 22] and grinding a mixture of Mg and Ni powders [10]. It is important to note the different conditions for obtaining both the mechanical alloy ($MgH_2 + 10$ wt. % Ni) and the kinetic curves of hydrogen desorption from it in [16, 22]: different temperatures and hydrogen pressures at which the kinetic curves of hydrogen desorption with MA were obtained. This fact practically does not allow to make a correct comparison of the experimental data received by various researchers and to define a way and conditions of reception of MAs which are capable to provide the best and stable hydrogen-sorption and kinetic characteristics in the conditions of cyclic work.

The purpose of this work was to study the role of the method and conditions of production, chemical state of the surface, the size factor in reducing the temperature and improving the decomposition kinetics of the nanosized MgH_2 hydride phase of mechanical alloys of magnesium with the transition metal Ni. To achieve this goal, a hydride-forming mechanical alloy of magnesium with 10 wt. % Ni in various manners was synthesized by the RMA method: reactive grinding of Mg powder with Ni, reactive grinding under the same conditions of two powders of MgH_2 with Ni produced by different methods. The effect of Ni additive and the method of obtaining MAs on the hydrogen sorption properties, temperature and kinetics of decomposition of its MgH_2 hydride phase has been investigated. It was assumed that, regardless of the method of preparation, the addition of Ni to magnesium would lead to an improvement in the kinetics and a decrease in the temperature of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase of the obtained MA due to the good catalytic properties of nickel and its effect on the chemical state of the surface. A probable dependence of the improvement of the hydrogen sorption and kinetic characteristics of the MgH_2 hydride phase on the method of its preparation was expected. The study of this dependence was also the purpose of this work.

We chose nickel as an alloying element because transition metals are known to have catalytic properties and, in the process of reactive mechanical synthesis, acting as dispersants, they can significantly improve the kinetics of magnesium hydrogenation/dehydrogenation of MgH_2 . According to theoretical predictions [11], transition metals significantly affect the thermodynamic stability of the hydride phase MgH_2 formed during the synthesis.

Therefore, the peculiarity of this work is that, the study of the kinetics of the process of hydrogen desorption from the synthesized mechanical alloys was performed at a constant normal hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor. Our experimental data obtained by the isobaric method on the installation of the original design of V.D. Dobrovolsky [12].

2. Materials and methods

The commercial powders of Mg, Ni (carbonyl) with a purity of 99.98 % and particles sizes of 100 and 3 μm , respectively, have been used as raw materials. Three mechanical alloys of the magnesium with an additive of 10 wt. % Ni, referred to MA1, MA2, MA3, are synthesized by reactive mechanical alloying (RMA) in different manners. Mechanical alloy MA1 was obtained by reactive grinding for 20 hours of Mg powder with Ni; mechanical alloy MA2 was derived by the same reactive grinding under the same conditions of MgH_2 powder (obtained by hydrogenation of Mg powder from the gas phase) with Ni additive. Mechanical alloy MA3 was obtained by another technique, in fact, by reactive grinding of magnesium powder for 10 hours, MgH_2 was obtained and after adding 10 wt. % Ni we continued grinding under a hydrogen atmosphere over 10 hours. The total reactive grinding time in the latter case, like in the case of MA1 and MA2, was 20 hours. For comparison, under the same conditions of reactive grinding of magnesium powder in a hydrogen atmosphere for 20 hours, a MgH_2 hydride phase without Ni (mechanical alloy MA4) was obtained. Mechanical alloying by reactive grinding of all powder mixtures was performed in a Retch100 ball mill with 10 mm steel balls in hydrogen atmosphere at a pressure of 1.2 MPa and a speed of 450 rpm. The ratio of the ball mass to the mass of the treated powder mixture was 20:1. Direct gas-phase hydrogenation (GPH) from MA1–MA4 materials was performed after being synthesized at a 5.0 MPa hydrogen pressure and 400 °C in the reactor. An automatic computerized DRON-3M diffractometer was employed for the X-ray phase and X-ray structural analysis of the samples. The X-Ray diffraction patterns were obtained using $CuK\alpha$ - radiation with a graphite monochromator. The profiles of diffraction lines were plotted with scanning steps of 0.1° and 15–20 sec exposure at each point of the spectrum. Crystal lattice parameters of the MgH_2 hydride phase in the obtained MAs and the volume of its unit cell were analyzed using Fullprof software Powder Cell 2.4 (<https://powdercell-for-windows.software.informer.com/2.4/>). The size of crystallites (grains) of the MgH_2 hydride phase in all MAs was determined by the approximation method according to Selyakov-Scherrer equation $D_{h,k,l} = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos \Theta$. The changes in the powder particles size upon mechanical milling were studied by a Super-Probe 733 scanning electron microscope. Investigations of the effect of Ni on hydrogen adsorption properties, thermal stability, kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase were performed by thermodesorption spectroscopy (TDS) on an automated computer system. An installation allows to obtain spectra and curves of hydrogen thermodesorption from hydride by isobaric method, i.e, to measure the volume of desorbed hydrogen from a sample heated at a given rate in a hydrogen medium at its constant reactor pressure of 0.1 MPa [12].

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) technique was used to explore in the present work the effect of exposure to air the mechanical alloy Mg + 10 wt. % Ni. The XPS spectra were studied with the UHV-Analysis-System (SPECS Surface Nano Analysis

Company, Germany). Briefly, the XPS spectra were excited with an X-ray Mg K α source ($E = 1253.6$ eV) and acquired at constant pass energy of 25 eV and at residual pressure of $(5-8) \times 10^{-10}$ mbar in the analysing chamber of the UHV-Analysis-System, which energy scale was calibrated employing pure reference copper and gold metals. The sample for the present XPS experiments was pressed in a rubbed pure copper plate with dimensions 10×10 mm².

3. Results and discussion

3.1 X-ray phase and X-ray diffraction analyzes

X-ray diffraction patterns from samples of mechanical alloys MA1, MA2, MA3 after their synthesis by the RMA method are shown in Fig. 1, and after their direct hydrogenation from the gas phase - in Fig. 2. Information on the phase composition of the MA samples obtained using RMA and after hydrogenation from the gas phase (GPH) is given in Table 1. The lattice parameters and unit cell volume for the MgH₂ hydride phase for MA1-MA4 are listed in Table 2. Crystallite size and average size particles of powders of mechanical alloys (after RMA) are presented in Table 3.

Table 1.

Phase composition of MA in the their first heating after reactive mechanical alloying (RMA) and after the first 5 cycles of their hydrogenation from the gaseous phase (HGP).

Mechanical alloys	Phase composition	
	RMA	HGP
MA1 (Mg+10wt. % Ni)	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO
MA2 (MgH ₂ +10wt. % Ni)	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO
MA3 (MgH ₂ +10wt. % Ni)	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO, Ni	MgH ₂ , Mg ₂ NiH ₄ , MgO, Ni
MA4 (Mg without Ni)	Mg, MgH ₂ , MgO	Mg, MgH ₂ , MgO

Fig. 1 - X-ray diffraction pattern of specimens of mechanical alloys after their synthesis by the RMA method: (a) - MA1; (b) - MA2; (c) - MA3.

Fig. 2 - X-ray diffraction pattern of specimens of mechanical alloys after their direct hydrogenation from the gaseous phase: (a) - MA1; (b) - MA2; (c) - MA3.

As can be seen from Fig. 1 and Table 1, the obtained mechanical alloys MA1, MA2, MA3 are composites as a result of reactive mechanical alloying with Ni. In addition to MgH_2 with a tetragonal structure, all MAs contain the hydride phase Mg_2NiH_4 and the MgO

phase, and reflections of metallic nickel can be seen on the diffractogram measured for the MA3 sample. After the first cycles of hydrogenation/dehydrogenation from the gas phase, all MAs reveal no changes in their phase composition.

Fig. 3 - X-ray diffraction pattern of specimen of non-commercial MgH_2 hydride.

Fig. 3 shows a diffractogram derived for a powder of non-commercial MgH_2 hydride, which we used to obtain the MA2 sample. This MgH_2 hydride was obtained by direct hydrogenation from the gaseous phase of magnesium powder with an average particle size of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ (in a Sieverts-type installation) at a temperature

of $400\ ^\circ\text{C}$ and a hydrogen pressure of $5\ \text{MPa}$ in the reactor. The average particle sizes of powders MA1, MA2, and MA3 determined based on the experimental data of scanning electron microscopy, after their synthesis (RMA) are found to be equal to 0.25 , 0.24 , $0.2\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively, and after hydrogenation from the gas phase in 5 cycle they are equal to 0.2 , 0.44 , $0.25\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Table 2.

Parameters of the crystal lattice (a,c) and the volume V of the unit cell for the nanosized MgH₂ hydride phase of mechanical alloys after their RMA and after the first 5 cycles of their hydrogenation from the gaseous phase (HGP).

Mechanical alloys	a,c – Å; V-Å ³	
	after RMA	after HGP
MA1	a = 4.5123 c = 3.0345 V = 62.256	a = 4.5132 c = 3.0170 V = 61.453
MA2	a = 4.5280 c = 3.0217 V = 61.953	a = 4.5154 c = 3.0209 V = 61.593
MA3	a = 4.5217 c = 3.0180 V = 61.705	a = 4.5141 c = 3.0208 V = 61.555
MA4	a = 4.5232 c = 3.0161 V = 61.707	a = 4.5140 c = 3.0195 V = 61.526

Table 3.

Average particle size, nanograins of the nanosized MgH₂ hydride phase of mechanical alloys after 20 hours of RMA and the first 5 cycles of their hydrogenation from the gaseous phase (HGP).

Mechanical alloys	The size of the crystallite d, nm		D _{part.} , μm
	after RMA	after HGP	RMA
MA1 (Mg+10wt. % Ni)	10.4	22.2	0.27
MA2 (MgH ₂ +10wt. % Ni)	12.6	29.2	0.32
MA3 (MgH ₂ +10wt. % Ni)	16.2	26.3	0.28
MA4 (Mg without Ni)	12	142	0.69

3.2 The thermal behavior of mechanical composite alloys MA1, MA2, MA3.

To determine the effect of Ni doping of the technique used for producing the MgH₂ hydride phase of the synthesized MA on its thermal stability and decomposition temperature, the process of hydrogen desorption from the MA1-MA4 samples by the TDS method

at a constant hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor and a sample heating rate of 3 deg/min was studied. The hydrogen desorption isobars obtained during the first heating after RMA of the MA1-MA4 samples are shown in Fig. 4, while those derived after the first hydrogenation from the gaseous phase are presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 - Isobars of hydrogen desorption obtained after synthesis by the method of RMA of mechanical alloys: (a) - MA1; (b) - MA2; (c) - MA3, (d) - MA4.

Fig. 5 - Isobars of hydrogen desorption after the first direct hydrogenation from the gaseous phase of mechanical alloys: (a) - MA1; (b) - MA2; (c) - MA3.

Based on the data of measurements of the hydrogen desorption isobars presented in Figs. 4 and 5, the capacities for hydrogen and the temperature of the onset of hydrogen desorption (T_{onset}) from the hydride phase MgH₂ of the MA1-MA4 samples were determined during heating the samples, both after their

mechanochemical synthesis (RMA) and after direct hydrogenation from the gaseous phase (HGP). The data obtained are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

The beginning temperature ($T_{\text{beg.}}$) of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase in MA1-MA4 and its hydrogen capacity

Mechanical alloys	after RMA		after HGP, 1st cycle hydrogenation	
	$T_{\text{beg.}}$, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	C_{H_2} % wt	$T_{\text{beg.}}$, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	C_{H_2} , % wt
MA1(Mg + 10 wt. % Ni)	295	6.1	295	5.94
MA2(MgH_2 + 10 wt. % Ni)	290	5.82	288	5.5
MA3(MgH_2 + 10 wt. % Ni)	283	5.4	283	5.33
MA4(Mg without Ni)	288	7.4	290	6.3

As can be seen from Figs. 4 and 5 as well as the data listed in Table 4, the beginning temperature ($T_{\text{beg.}}$) from samples of the mechanical alloys-composites MA1-MA4 after their synthesis by the RMA was 295, 290, 283, 288 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. After the first HGP of these MAs, the $T_{\text{beg.}}$ was determined to be equal to 295, 288, 283, and 290 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Noteworthy is that, these temperatures can be considered the beginning temperatures of hydrogen desorption from the main MgH_2 hydride phase, given the smaller number of other hydride phases Mg_2NiH_4 affecting the MC1-MC3 samples and the impossibility to record the beginning of the hydrogen release experimentally. When comparing the T_{beg} values in Table 4 for hydrogen desorption (release) from undoped by Ni the MgH_2 phase in MA4 (288 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa) with the same temperature for MA1-MA3, virtually no effect of additive Ni and method of obtaining MAs on the beginning temperature of hydrogen desorption and the associated beginning temperature of their MgH_2 hydride phase decomposition can be stated for all the MAs. We also did not observe the expected decrease in the equilibrium decomposition temperature of the hydride MgH_2 phase of the above mechanical alloys at a hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa (288 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ according to [33]), which would indicate a decrease in the thermodynamic stability of the MgH_2 phase due to its mechanical alloying with nickel. In our opinion, the explanation for the absence of a decrease in the thermodynamic stability of MgH_2 due to the mechanical alloying by Ni may be the fact that, under the conditions of the methods used to obtain the MAs (and, consequently, their main hydride phase MgH_2), no solid solution of Ni in magnesium is formed. According to [11], the $\text{Mg}(\text{Ni})\text{H}_2$ hydride should have

a lower enthalpy of formation than the enthalpy of formation of MgH_2 , and hence its lower thermodynamic stability and decomposition temperature. As shown by X-ray phase analysis, evidence of the fact that under the conditions of the synthesis of the MA1, MA2, and MA3 samples by the RMA method, $\text{Mg}(\text{Ni})\text{H}_2$ hydride was practically not formed or was formed in a very insignificant amount, may be the presence of the Mg_2NiH_4 phase in the composition of all the MAs, the formation of which was significantly associated with the amount of the alloying element Ni; as well as the absence of the expected decrease in the unit cell volume of the hydride phase of MgH_2 of the MA1, MA2, MA3 samples in comparison with that of the hydride phase MgH_2 without Ni additives (Table 2).

3.3 Kinetics of the hydrogen desorption from the mechanical alloys-composites MA1, MA2, MA3 obtained by different techniques

The kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase in all synthesized MAs after their HGP under the same conditions has been investigated at temperatures of 310 and 330 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a constant hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor. Isobaric-isothermal kinetic curves of hydrogen desorption for the MA1, MA2, MA3 samples at temperature of 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ are shown in Fig. 6. For comparison, Fig. 7 shows the kinetic curve of hydrogen desorption from the mechanical alloy MA4 (without the additive of Ni), which was obtained under the same conditions as the mechanical alloy MA1. The data on the release time of half of the total amount of hydrogen ($\tau_{1/2}$) and the total amount of hydrogen (τ_f) for all the MAs are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5.

Time (min) of release of half ($\tau_{1/2}$) and total amount hydrogen (τ_f) from mechanical alloys at temperatures of 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 330 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and constant hydrogen pressure 0.1 MPa.

Mechanical alloys	310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$		330 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	
	$\tau_{1/2}$	τ_f	$\tau_{1/2}$	τ_f
MA1 (Mg + 10 wt. % Ni)	2.2	7	1.6	5
MA2 (MgH_2 + 10 wt. % Ni)	3.4	10	2.5	7
MA3 (MgH_2 + 10 wt. % Ni)	3.5	10	1.6	5
MA4 (Mg without Ni)	55	160	30	80

Fig. 6 - Kinetic curves of hydrogen desorption from mechanical alloys MA1, MA2, MA3, obtained at hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor and different temperatures: (a) -310°C , (b) -330°C .

Fig. 7 - Kinetic curve of hydrogen desorption from the mechanical alloy MA4 obtained at hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa in the reactor and temperature of 330°C .

Analysis of the experimental data listed in Table 5 allows for concluding that addition to magnesium of 10 wt % Ni when synthesizing the MA1, MA2, MA3 samples significantly improves the kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH_2 hydride phase of these alloys-nanocomposite. It is evidenced by the experimentally recorded 16-fold, 11-fold and 13-fold reduction of the total desorbed hydrogen release time for MA1, MA2, MA3, respectively, at a constant temperature of 330°C and the constant pressure of 0.1 MPa compared with the time of releasing all amount of hydrogen in the case of MA4 (Table 5, column " 330°C "). Liang et al. [2] have demonstrated that the 3d-metal additives could drastically reduce the activation energy of desorption for magnesium hydride. Hanada et al. [34] have also observed a decrease in the activation energy of hydrogen desorption of MgH_2 doped with transition metals (Ni, Fe, Co, Cu). Lei Xie et al. [16] have found that the ad-

dition of 10 wt. % Ni to MgH_2 reduces desorption activation energy from 191 kJ/mol to 118 kJ/mol. However, the operating temperature was still too high for practical applications and the catalytic mechanism of Ni is unclear [16]. Our X-ray photoelectron spectra of Mg 2s, Mg 2p, O1s, C1s core-level electrons measured for the sample MA1 and, for comparison, from the sample MA4 (which are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively) indicate almost the same chemical state of the surface of these MAs formed after their synthesis by the RMA method and subsequent exposure to air for one day. Given this result, it is logical to assume that when adding 10 wt. % Ni, the above 16-fold reduction in the release time of all amount of hydrogen from MA1 (compared to MA4) is mainly due to a decrease in the activation energy of hydrogen desorption from MgH_2 , and not due to changes in the chemical state of the surface of the particles of the MA1 powder.

Fig. 8 – XPS (a) Mg 2s, (b) Mg 2p, (c) O 1s, (d) C 1s core-level spectra of the specimen of MA1 derived by reactive mechanical alloying and exposed to air for one day.

Fig. 9 - XPS (a) Mg 2s, (b) Mg 2p, (c) O 1s, (d) C 1s core-level spectra of the specimen of MA4 derived by reactive mechanical alloying and exposed to air for one day.

The analysis and comparison of the data listed in Table 5 for the MA1 and MA2 samples allow stating that a method of reactive grinding of the Mg +10 wt % Ni powder mixture (rather than grinding a powder mixture of MgH₂ +10 wt. % Ni) reveals the best kinetic characteristics of the mechanical alloys. As shown in Table 5, the time needed to release half of total hydrogen $\tau_{1/2}$ from the sample MA1 (Mg + 10 wt. % Ni) and its total amount τ_f at temperature of 330 °C is 1.6 and 5 minutes, respectively. For the MA2 sample (MgH₂ + 10 wt. % Ni), these values are found to be 2.5 and 7 minutes, respectively.

Such an outcome appeared rather unexpected for the authors since most researchers used reactive grinding of Ni powder with MgH₂ powder rather than Mg powder to improve the kinetics of the hydrogen desorption from the MgH₂ hydride phase doped with transition metals (Ni, Fe, Ti) in synthesized MAs. To explain this outcome, the crystallites (grains) size of the MgH₂ hydride phase was determined to be 29.2 and 22.2 nm for MA2 (MgH₂ + 10 wt. % Ni) and MA1 (Mg + 10 wt. % Ni), respectively, using the obtained X-ray diffraction patterns and the approximation method according to Selyakov-Scherrer equation $D_{h,k,l} = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos \Theta$ after the first 5 cycles of their HGP (Table 1). Based on these data, it is logical to assume that the faster kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH₂ hydride phase in MA1 (Mg + 10 wt. % Ni) may be due to the smaller grain size (and correspondingly shorter diffusion paths for hydrogen atoms) compared to grain size of the MgH₂ hydride phase in MA2 (MgH₂ + 10 wt. % Ni). The experimentally established higher value of the release time of all amount of hydrogen τ_f for MA3 in comparison with τ_f for MA1 can also be attributed to the larger size of crystallites (grains) of the hydride phase MgH₂ in MA3 (26.2 nm) than in MA1 (22.2 nm). Thus, given the data in Tables 3 and 5, relating to the size of the crystallites (grains) d (nm) and the time of release of all amount of hydrogen τ_f (min) in MA1, MA2, MA3, we can say about the existence of a correlation between the release time of all amount of hydrogen from these MAs and the size of the crystallites (grains) of their hydride phase MgH₂ that depends on the method of obtaining the studied mechanical alloys-nanocomposites.

An interesting and important fact is noteworthy when analyzing the data listed in Table 3. After 5 cycles of heating/cooling the MA1, MA2, MA3 samples during their HGP, the grain size of the MgH₂ hydride phase increases by 2.13; 2.32 and 1.62 times, respectively. However, under the same conditions of cyclic heating/cooling of the MA4 sample (without Ni), an increase in the grains of the MgH₂ hydride phase from 12 nm to 142 nm (almost 12 times) can be observed. This observation enables drawing a meaningful conclusion about the influence of nickel on the stability of the performance characteristics in studied Mg-based mechanical alloys with a Ni additive. By preventing the grain sizes of the MgH₂ hydride phase from growing, Ni ensures the stability of its nanostructure during cyclic operation and, thus, the stability of its operating kinetic and hydrogen sorption characteristics.

Hence, Ni as an additive to magnesium during synthesis of the MA1, MA2 and MA3 samples by the RMA method acts as a dispersant and nanostructure stabilizer during cyclic operation of these MAs, inhibiting the growth of crystallites (grains) in the MgH₂ hydride phase.

Conclusion

Three mechanical alloys based on magnesium with the addition of 10 wt. % Ni (MA1, MA2, MA3) were synthesized by one method of reactive mechanical alloying (RMA), however in different manners. The hydrogen capacity, thermal stability, and kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the nanosized MgH₂ hydride phase of the obtained MAs were studied using thermodesorption spectroscopy at a constant hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa.

It has been established that the time needed for the total hydrogen release from MA1, MA2, MA3, was 7, 11, 9 min and 5, 7, 6 min, respectively, at a constant hydrogen pressure of 0.1 MPa and temperatures of 310 and 330 °C respectively.

The method of obtaining a mechanical alloy by reactive grinding of Mg +10 wt. % Ni powder mixture rather than MgH₂ +10 wt. % Ni powder mixture has been shown to improve the kinetic characteristics. Faster kinetics of hydrogen desorption from the MgH₂ hydride phase of MA1 (Mg + 10 wt. % Ni) was due to the smaller grain size than the grain size of the MgH₂ hydride phase in MA2 (MgH₂ + 10 wt. % Ni).

The correlation between the time τ_f (min) of the release of all amount of hydrogen from mechanical alloys MA1, MA2, and MA3 and the size of crystallites (grains) of their MgH₂ hydride phase, which depends on the method of obtaining these MAs has been established.

The role of the alloying element Ni in improving the kinetics of the process of desorption of hydrogen from MAs obtained in different manners, as well as in stabilizing their nanostructure during cyclic operation by preventing (inhibiting) the growth of the crystallite (grain) of their MgH₂ hydride phase has been elucidated.

It has been established the practical absence of the influence of Ni additive and the manner of obtaining MAs on the temperature of the beginning of hydrogen desorption and the associated temperature of the beginning of decomposition of the nanosized MgH₂ hydride phase of the mechanical alloys MA1, MA2, and MA3, as well as on the chemical state of their surface.

Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that this article content has no conflict of interest.

All authors of this manuscript have directly participated in planning, execution, and analysis of this study.

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